

Energy-Matter Equivalence: Cosmological Constant Revisited

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October 19, 2024

Abstract

The existence of cosmological constant in Einstein Field Equation has been on debate for a long time. And the weight of photon regarding the energy-mass equivalence equation has been not determined, yet. In this paper, the method of reducing cosmological constant in Einstein Field Equation into geodesic notation in Theory of Special Relativity would be demonstrated. And the weight of particle with rule of conservation regarding the energy-mass equivalence would be suggested. Conventional wisdom of verifying what we know repeatedly time-to-time in order to know true has been proven true, again. And with improvement of scientific knowledge in time, such as particle in here, it turned out that any given knowledge assumed to be true has to be modified in order to be correct. In conclusion, use of cosmological constant can be excluded in theory of relativity. And assumption of Einstein seems to be correct in energy-matter equivalence, but its representation in equation has to be modified with knowledge of modern physics.

Keywords: Cosmological constant, Energy-matter equivalence

1 Introduction

The reason of use in cosmological constant in Einstein Field Equation is still in debate[Stephani et al.(2009)Stephani, Kramer, The difference made is a difference in Special Relativity Theory and General Relativity Theory. General assumption of use in cosmological constant made different result in mathematics and physics. In this paper, this viewpoint would be unified in form of interaction.

2 Inevitable Distortion

It is well known that distortion of spacetime is inevitable with what has mass. But what has been discussed as geodesic in special relativity retains error ratio in general relativity theory by cosmological constant. Inevitable distortion in spacetime has met inevitable distortion by cosmological constant. How can it be explained?

2.1 Geodesics between Theory of Relativity

In theory of special relativity, it is explained that geodesics follow in form of norm as:

$$E = \gamma mc^2 \text{ s.t. } \gamma = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}$$

On the other hand in theory of general relativity, it is explained that Minkowski gets transformed in tensor as:

$$\begin{aligned} R_{\mu\nu} - \frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu} &= \Lambda g_{\mu\nu} + G_{\mu\nu} \\ \implies g_{\mu\nu}(\Lambda + \frac{1}{2}R) &= G_{\mu\nu} - R_{\mu\nu} \end{aligned}$$

This implies Minkowski space defined as energy-stress tensor($g_{\mu\nu}$) with its own scalar curvature in Einstein field equation is decided with difference in metric tensor($G_{\mu\nu}$) and Ricci tensor($R_{\mu\nu}$). But for understanding more than this, we face conventional difference of cosmological constant Λ , making mathematical definition unmatched with geodesic in differential geometry. This difference in mathematics and physics made much doubt on how mathematics can be an adequate tool for describing reality. If specialized forms are generalized in tensor form, geodesic as special relativity in γ should have equal meaning with $\frac{1}{2}Rg_{\mu\nu}$. But in measuring reality, the approximation error by $\Lambda g_{\mu\nu}$ seems un-mathematical in sense of definition in geodesic.

We would discuss on how omitted assumptions made unclear existence between norm-driven special relativity and curvature-driven general relativity.

2.2 Einstein Field Equation in Cauchy-Schwarz Equation

By any mean of generalization, curvature rate R in differential manifold S should have a meaning in given time T as:

$$R = \min_T \sum \frac{\|d\vec{S}\|}{dT} \quad (1)$$

For we know that geodesic is the shortest path from any cut point to another in any topological object:

$$R = \min_T \int \left\| \nabla \cdot \vec{S} \sqrt{1 - \frac{\nabla^2}{c^2}} \right\| dT \quad (2)$$

But with cosmological constant Λ , geodesic for energy-stress tensor given becomes:

$$\gamma_{Generalized} = \Lambda + \frac{1}{2}R = \frac{1}{2} \left(2\Lambda + \min_T \int \left\| \nabla \cdot \vec{S} \sqrt{1 - \frac{\nabla^2}{c^2}} \right\| dT \right) \quad (3)$$

This difference makes unfitness with geodesic defined in special relativity of $\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}$. Then why?

3 Cauchy-Schwarz Inequality Equation with Theory of Relativity

This unfit difference can be explained with expansion process of Cauchy-Schwarz inequality equation. For sequences in $x, y \in \mathbb{R}^n$ [Steele(2004)]:

$$|\langle x, y \rangle|^2 \leq \langle x, x \rangle \langle y, y \rangle \quad (4)$$

For generally expanding upper equation:

$$|x_1y_1 + x_2y_2 + \dots|^2 \leq (x_1x_1 + x_2x_2 + \dots)(y_1y_1 + y_2y_2 + \dots) \quad (5)$$

With giving assumption of sequence x and y being vector:

$$(\|x_1y_1\| + \|x_2y_2\| + \dots)^2 \leq (\|x_1x_1\| + \|x_2x_2\| + \dots)(\|y_1y_1\| + \|y_2y_2\| + \dots) \quad (6)$$

By giving assumption that giving any sequence being subject to be velocity vector in observation, geodesic changes in special relativity as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\gamma_1 \|x_1y_1\| + \gamma_2 \|x_2y_2\| + \dots)^2 \\ & \leq (\gamma_1 \|x_1x_1\| + \gamma_2 \|x_2x_2\| + \dots)(\gamma_1 \|y_1y_1\| + \gamma_2 \|y_2y_2\| + \dots) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

The problem of difference between special and general relativity derives as expand in exposition of general relativity tensor notation in multiplier of each vector term:

$$\begin{aligned} & (\gamma_1 \|x_1y_1\| + \gamma_1\gamma_2 \|x_2y_2\| + \dots)^2 \\ & \leq (\gamma_1 \|x_1x_1\| + \gamma_1\gamma_2 \|x_2x_2\| + \dots)(\gamma_1 \|y_1y_1\| + \gamma_1\gamma_2 \|y_2y_2\| + \dots) \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

It was not the mathematics that is wrong, but the assumption in use of tensor without considering timely accumulation was making possible error term. By admitting timely accumulation, geodesics used in general and special relativity can remain same.

4 Weight of Photon

Furthermore, this implies the possible solution in defining weight of photon. The problem with photon weight is of its existence – Is the weight of photon zero [Smarandache et al.(2013)Smarandache, Yuhua, and Fengjuan]? Assuming weight of photon to be zero makes clashes with Newton dynamics, but to be not zero makes clashes with assumptions of Einstein energy-matter equivalence equation.

$$E = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}} mc^2$$

With changes in mass of photon, energy-matter equivalence cannot be true. The classical solution for this phenomenon is to define inertia to be different from gravity, making Newton field different from Einstein field. But same meaning for mass of photon should be differed between Newton and Einstein dynamics seems irrational. Then how can this be unified?

5 Electron in Two Photon Particles: Geodesic of Space

The answer is in the energy-matter equivalence equation itself. With assumption in conservation of energy, geodesic given by single equivalence must be divided in two terms with m_p being mass of particle in full-integer spin followed by Einstein-Boson statistics.

$$E = \gamma(m + m_p)c^2 = \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}mc^2 + \frac{1}{\sqrt{1 - \frac{v^2}{c^2}}}m_p c^2$$

This change of difference makes notation change of density in overall matter with velocity. This equation implies two aspects.

1. It is important to verify whether what we know as true is true, always.
2. The importance of verification is not correlated with the impact of what we know.

6 Conclusion: Two Worlds, One Family

With discussion here, we unified geodesic concept used in general and special relativity, and verified the possible error that energy-matter equivalence has. To list them up:

1. There is no need of regarding the relation between special and general relativity being not the same.
2. Einstein's energy-matter equivalence equation has to be modified with consideration of mass in photon.

References

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